

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D1.3

ONLINE CRM-GEOTHERMAL FLUID ATLAS FOR EUROPE AND EASTERN AFRICA

Summary:

Deliverable D1.3 presents the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas, an interactive, GIS-based online platform that visualises geothermal and critical raw material (CRM) data across Europe and Eastern Africa.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D1.3 presents the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas, an interactive, GIS-based online platform that visualises and integrates geospatial and geochemical data related to geothermal fluids and associated critical raw materials (CRMs) across Europe and Eastern Africa. The Atlas represents the third major outcome of Work Package 1, building directly upon the data harmonisation (D1.1) (Seres et al. 2024) and database publication (D1.2) (Seres et al. 2025). It transforms the harmonised datasets of the CRM-geothermal database into a spatially oriented, user-friendly tool that enables exploration, comparison, and interpretation of CRM-relevant geothermal data in a geoscientific context.

The Atlas combines legacy data from literature and previous projects with newly generated datasets obtained during CRM-geothermal field campaigns and laboratory analyses. It provides an integrated visualisation of geochemical, geological, and geothermal information across regions of strategic interest for CRM recovery and geothermal development.

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas integrates and visualises multiple data layers, including site locations, geothermal wells, fluid samples, rock and scale compositions, and selected CRM concentrations. Each data point on the map is linked to its corresponding metadata record and DOI, enabling users to trace data provenance, citation, and licensing information. The platform's interactive functionalities allow users to filter, query, and export data by parameter, site, country, or CRM element, supporting both scientific analysis and strategic decision-making.

Technically, the Fluid Atlas is implemented as a web-based GIS application, developed with open-source tools and interoperable standards. The system architecture combines a PostgreSQL/PostGIS spatial database with a web interface that connects directly to the CRM-geothermal data repository. This ensures continuous synchronisation of updates from the main database, so that newly added datasets and metadata become immediately visible in the online Atlas.

Geographically, the Fluid Atlas covers key geothermal provinces in Europe and Eastern Africa, including Türkiye, Iceland, Italy, Germany, and the East African Rift region (Kenya, Tanzania, Ethiopia). The inclusion of these regions allows comparative analysis of geothermal systems in different geological and tectonic settings, contributing to a broader understanding of the distribution and enrichment of critical raw materials in geothermal environments.

The online platform is publicly accessible at <https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu> and supports multiple user roles:

- Public users can search, visualize and export datasets.
- Registered Users can additionally upload and edit data but may edit only their own uploads.
- Administrators have full privileges on all data and can approve or remove user registrations

By providing a single, interactive gateway to high-quality CRM-geothermal data, the Fluid Atlas contributes to open science, data-driven innovation, and sustainable resource management. It enhances the visibility and impact of project results and ensures the long-term availability of data beyond the lifetime of the project through integration with European geological data infrastructures.

2 INTRODUCTION

The CRM-geothermal project addresses Europe's growing need for sustainable and diversified sources of critical raw materials (CRMs) by exploring their potential recovery from geothermal fluids. These fluids, circulating deep within the Earth's crust, can host valuable concentrations of metals and elements such as lithium, strontium, rare earth elements, and platinum-group elements. The project focuses on regions where geothermal energy production and CRM potential coexist – in particular, selected sites across Europe and Eastern Africa.

An important component of the project outcomes is the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas, an online GIS-based platform designed to visualise and explore geospatial data on geothermal systems and associated CRMs. The Atlas builds directly upon the work presented in deliverables D1.1 (data collection and harmonisation) and D1.2 (data publication). While D1.2 focused on creating and publishing the CRM-geothermal database as a FAIR-compliant, open-access repository, D1.3 translates these harmonised datasets into a dynamic spatial environment. The result is an interactive, map-based tool that allows users to access, analyse, and interpret geothermal and CRM data within their geological context.

The Fluid Atlas also acts as a dissemination tool. Through WP6 (Dissemination and Communication), the Atlas serves as a key vehicle for sharing project results with scientific, industrial, and policy audiences, increasing the project's visibility and societal relevance. The platform thus functions as both a scientific data tool and a communication interface that supports open science and stakeholder engagement.

The geographic scope of the Fluid Atlas extends across the European continent and the East African Rift, covering diverse geological environments such as the volcanic and sedimentary systems of Türkiye, the geothermal fields of Iceland, the engineered systems in Cornwall (UK), and the active rift zones of Kenya and Tanzania. This broad coverage enables users to conduct comparative analyses of geothermal fluids and CRM occurrences across different tectonic and geochemical settings, providing valuable insights for future exploration and sustainable resource management.

In addition to its scientific role, the Fluid Atlas is designed as a long-term digital infrastructure for data preservation and accessibility. It integrates with the CRM-geothermal database backend, automatically synchronising newly published datasets, and adheres to international data-sharing standards such as INSPIRE and Dublin Core. Its open-source architecture ensures interoperability with European geological data infrastructures, notably EGDI (European Geological Data Infrastructure) and EPOS (European Plate Observing System), guaranteeing continuity beyond the lifetime of the CRM-geothermal project.

The recent deliverable provides both the conceptual and technical documentation of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas. It demonstrates how harmonised geothermal and CRM-related data can be transformed into a comprehensive, GIS-based visualisation and decision-support tool. Through this deliverable, the project reinforces its commitment to FAIR data principles, open science, and long-term sustainability, ensuring that the Fluid Atlas remains a lasting resource for researchers, industry, and policymakers involved in Europe's transition to a more resilient and resource-efficient future.

3 PRINCIPLES AND FAIR DATA FRAMEWORK

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas was conceived as an interactive, GIS-based platform that transforms the harmonised datasets of the CRM-geothermal database into a spatially integrated and user-oriented information system. Its core purpose is to make geochemical and geological information collected within the project accessible, interpretable, and reusable for both scientific and non-scientific audiences. Building on the data collection and publication framework established in Deliverable D1.2, the Atlas extends the database with a geospatial interface that enables users to explore and compare CRM-related geothermal data through maps, thematic layers, and location-based visualisation (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1: Conceptual overview of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas. Existing and newly generated datasets flow into the central CRM-geothermal database, which feeds the GIS-based visualisation platform.

The Atlas serves as the visual gateway to the CRM-geothermal database. Through its web-based interface, users can search, filter, and download datasets, examine analytical and metadata records, and compare parameters across regions or geological settings. Each dataset contains references, ensuring traceability, citation, and proper data provenance. The interface supports both exploratory and analytical use, allowing scientific users to identify patterns such as REE enrichment or scaling tendencies, while also providing clear visual communication for policymakers, industry, and the public.

Interactivity and modularity were key design principles. The system accommodates new datasets and functionalities as the project evolves, with automatic synchronisation between the CRM-geothermal database and the Fluid Atlas. This ensures that newly published records become immediately available on the platform. The same design supports the long-term goal of maintaining the Atlas as a living infrastructure that continues to grow beyond the project’s lifetime.

To ensure openness and interoperability, the Atlas was developed according to FAIR data and open-science principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (*Figure 2, Table 1*).

- Findability is achieved through structured metadata and a detailed reference list.
- Accessibility is ensured by open web access at <https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu>, offering free visualisation and xlsx download.
- Interoperability relies on widely accepted standards such as Dublin Core, INSPIRE, and EPOS/EGDI metadata schemes, combined with open-source technologies, including

PostgreSQL/PostGIS for data management, Node.js with Express for the REST API backend (serving data in JSON/GeoJSON format), and Angular with Leaflet for the web-based map interface.

- Reusability is guaranteed by the inclusion of analytical metadata, QA/QC information, and standard units, enabling data to be reinterpreted in future scientific or industrial contexts.

Figure 2: FAIR data principles in the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas.

Table 1: Overview of FAIR principle implementation in the Fluid Atlas

FAIR Principle	Implementation in the Fluid Atlas	Standards/Tools Applied
Findable	Datasets linked to references with DOIs and structured metadata	DOIs via Zenodo/GFZ, Dublin Core
Accessible	Open web interface, download options	XLSX
Interoperable	Compliance with EU and OGC standards; open, machine-readable data exchange via JSON/GeoJSON	INSPIRE, EPOS/EGDI, EPSG:4326
Reusable	Complete metadata, QA/QC, provenance	Standardised schema, FAIR lifecycle

Beyond ensuring interoperability and open access, the Fluid Atlas also applies a rigorous quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) framework to maintain data integrity. Quality Assurance (QA) procedures include the use of harmonised data templates, controlled vocabularies, and standardised analytical protocols agreed among project partners. Quality Control (QC) involves automated and manual validation of data values, units, coordinates, and metadata completeness before publication. Together, these processes ensure that all datasets visualised in the Atlas are reliable, traceable, and consistent across study regions.

The Atlas is hosted and maintained by the University of Miskolc, with technical collaboration from

project partners GFZ and LPRC. The infrastructure ensures secure HTTPS access, regular backups, and version-controlled updates. Role-based permissions mirror the CRM-geothermal database structure: public users can visualise and download data, registered users can upload and edit their own datasets, and administrators manage validation and publication.

4 DATA SOURCES AND CONTENT

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas builds directly upon the harmonised and curated datasets developed within the CRM-geothermal Database (Deliverable D1.2). It extends these datasets into a spatially referenced and visually interactive environment, integrating both pre-existing and newly generated data into a single, coherent framework.

The database integrates two main categories of data:

- Existing (legacy) datasets compiled from literature and previous research initiatives, and
- New datasets obtained through CRM-geothermal field sampling, laboratory analysis, and experimental work.

Both categories are stored in the CRM-geothermal database and visualised in the Atlas using harmonised metadata structures and consistent coordinate systems.

Existing data, forming the foundation of the CRM-geothermal database, were collected and harmonised under Deliverable D1.1 – Data Collection and Harmonisation, drawing on peer-reviewed literature, national geological databases, and previous European projects such as REFLECT and PERFORM.

These datasets represent a broad spectrum of geothermal environments, including high-enthalpy volcanic systems, sedimentary basins, and engineered geothermal systems, providing baseline information on fluid compositions, physical parameters, and rock–fluid interaction processes.

New datasets have been produced through systematic field sampling and laboratory analysis conducted by project partners in Türkiye (Tuzla and Seferihisar), the East African Rift (Kenya, Tanzania), and Cornwall (UK). These activities generated detailed geochemical, mineralogical, and physical data covering fluids, rocks, gases, and precipitates.

Each record includes references to its original publication, ensuring traceability and citation integrity. Metadata fields (e.g. CRM-geothermal database IDs, location, sampling depth, chemical composition, analytical method, and uncertainty) follow the schema defined in Annex 1 of D1.2. In the Fluid Atlas, data are visualised as spatially linked well records that display associated measurements and geochemical characteristics of geothermal fluids, rocks, and related critical raw materials (CRMs). These harmonised datasets enable comparative studies, trend analyses, and identification of potential knowledge gaps across regions.

Each dataset type is represented as a separate sheet within the database structure, corresponding to a specific category of geothermal data (*Table 2*).

Table 2: Contents and main attribute types of the different data sheets

Sheet	Description / Content	Core Attributes Displayed
Wells	Boreholes associated with geothermal projects	Well ID, depth, lithology, temperature, operator
Fluids	Water and brine samples from geothermal wells and surface discharges	Temperature, pH, major ions (Na, K, Ca, Mg, Cl, SO ₄), trace CRMs (Li, Sr, Cs, REE, PGE)
Rocks	Core or cuttings samples from wells or outcrops	Lithology, mineralogy, trace elements, CRM concentrations
Scales / Precipitates	Mineral deposits from geothermal installations	Mineral phases, deposition environment, CRM enrichment
Gases	Free or dissolved gases sampled from wells or vents	Gas composition (CO ₂ , CH ₄ , H ₂ , He, N ₂), isotopic signatures

5 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 OVERALL SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas operates as a single-page web application developed in Angular, integrating a Leaflet-based interactive map interface. The platform connects to an internal REST API, implemented in Node.js with the Express framework, which retrieves data directly from the central MySQL database (Figure 3).

This architecture ensures a seamless flow of harmonised geoscientific and geochemical information between the backend and the client interface. The REST API endpoints (e.g. /api/scale-sample-data) deliver results in JSON/GeoJSON format, supporting lightweight and interoperable data exchange.

The web server stack runs on Ubuntu, with nginx acting as reverse proxy and static file host, while the Express backend provides secure HTTPS communication and token-based authentication. This configuration enables controlled data access and scalable performance. This modern web architecture fully complies with FAIR and open-science principles.

Figure 3. Overview of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas architecture and data flow

5.2 DATA FLOW AND SYNCHRONISATION

The Fluid Atlas is directly linked to the CRM-geothermal database, ensuring synchronisation between records and the web interface. Each dataset published through the project’s data-collection workflow (Deliverable D1.2) becomes immediately available in the Atlas once approved.

Data are transmitted as JSON objects through secure REST calls and visualised in real time on the client side. This design guarantees consistency and up-to-date visualisation across all thematic layers, while allowing new CRM-related datasets or analytical results to be integrated without code modification.

5.3 WEB APPLICATION FUNCTIONALITY

The web interface allows users to search, filter, and visualise geothermal datasets by location, parameter type, or geological context. These filtered datasets can then be exported to xlsx format for further analytical use (Figure 4). Essential metadata, including analytical details and references, are displayed to ensure traceability and data provenance. The Leaflet engine supports interactive maps, layer control, and pop-up metadata, enabling both scientific and public exploration.

Figure 4: User interaction workflow in the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas

5.4 HOSTING, SECURITY, AND MAINTENANCE

The Fluid Atlas is hosted and maintained by the University of Miskolc (Institute of Information Technology), in collaboration with GFZ and LPRC. The infrastructure ensures secure HTTPS access, role-based permissions, and regular backups. All client-server communication is encrypted, with authentication tokens issued per session. Version-controlled updates and scheduled maintenance guarantee stability and long-term sustainability.

6 USER ACCESS, ROLES AND DATA MANAGEMENT

This chapter describes how access rights, user roles, and data management are implemented in the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas to ensure transparency, quality control, and data integrity.

6.1 USER ROLES AND DATABASE PROTECTION

Access rights follow the structure of the CRM-geothermal database:

- Public users can search, visualise, and download published datasets.
- Registered users can additionally upload and edit data, but may modify only their own uploads.
- Administrators have full privileges on all data and can approve or remove user registrations.

This role-based permission model ensures that users have access only to the functions necessary for their level of responsibility, maintaining both security and traceability within the system.

To ensure data quality, automatic registration has been disabled. Anyone wishing to register in order to contribute to the database must request access by email from one of the administrators. After verifying that the applicant is a professional in the geothermal field, the administrators can grant registered-user access.

Registered users may upload, delete, or modify data; however, to prevent accidental deletion or modification of the entire database and to preserve its integrity and quality, they can only edit or remove the data they have uploaded themselves. This controlled registration process safeguards the reliability of the data and ensures that contributions originate from qualified professionals.

6.2 DATA SUBMISSION AND QUALITY

All datasets uploaded by registered users or administrators follow the data-submission and validation procedures established in Deliverable D1.2. There are two ways to submit data to the Fluid Atlas database. The first is to use the harmonised Excel data templates, fill them in, and import the completed files into the web database. The Excel templates include detailed guidelines, controlled vocabularies, a harmonised metadata structure, and built-in data validation rules, such as required format, maximum solubility values for many elements and anion–cation charge balance checks. The second option is to use the built-in data entry interface of the Fluid Atlas and Database web application. This interface also has detailed guidelines, vocabularies, mandatory fields and follows the same harmonized metadata structure.

The data currently stored in the database has also undergone quality control through both automated and manual validation of data values and units. IDs were harmonized, coordinates transformed into WGS84, decimal degrees, invalid values, like pH above 14 were removed, missing values filled in where possible (TDG, TDS, reservoir type) and most importantly, as because many errors existed in external databases, numbers given in different units were converted into the SI units used by CRM-geothermal.

The validation workflow ensures that every dataset displayed in the Atlas is accurate, traceable, and compliant with the project's FAIR data framework.

7 DATA VISUALISATION AND ANALYTICAL FEATURES

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas combines database and map views to support the visualisation, search, import, and export of geothermal data. All spatial information is based on wells, these are the items shown on the map. Other datasets, fluids, gases, rocks, and scales, are linked to wells and can be accessed through their corresponding well records. This structure ensures consistency between the relational database and the map interface. A detailed user guide of the CRM-geothermal database and Fluid Atlas is provided in *Annex 1*.

7.1 MAP INTERFACE

The Map view displays wells as circular markers that dynamically aggregate multiple records depending on the zoom level. Each circle represents one or more well records in the database, and the number displayed within the circle indicates how many wells are located within the given area (visible when hovering over the marker). This approach improves map readability at smaller scales, where large numbers of wells would otherwise overlap and obscure the underlying map.

Selecting a well shows the ID of it in the list on the left-hand panel. Clicking on it opens its data view window showing the well attributes and the IDs of any related fluid, gas, rock, or scale records, which can be opened directly (Figure 5).

Navigation tools allow users to zoom, pan, and select wells by clicking on markers or by drawing a selection box. The background uses OpenStreetMap tiles, providing an open, lightweight base for visualisation.

Figure 5: Map view of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and Database tool.

7.2 SEARCH AND ADVANCED SEARCH

Two search options are available throughout the application (Figure 6):

General search: a free-text search that scans the active sheet (for example, the Well sheet) for any occurrence of the entered characters. It is unrestricted by field or attribute but applies only to the active sheet. W-well, F-fluid, R-rock, G-gas, S-scale

Advanced search (filter): a structured, attribute-based search that allows users to specify one or more criteria, possibly from different sheets, combined by an AND relation. This enables complex queries, such as finding wells within a defined temperature range that also contain specific fluid-chemistry records. The Advanced Search therefore functions as the system’s filter tool, narrowing the dataset according to user-defined parameters.

Figure 6: Search and advanced search (filter) options in the Tool.

7.3 DATA IMPORT

New records can be added to the database in two ways:

Excel import: Registered users and administrators can import data directly from the official harmonised CRM-geothermal Excel template (available at <https://crm-geothermal.eu> or at the Appendix in Database view). The file must conform exactly to the template’s structure, which includes controlled vocabularies, harmonised metadata, and predefined validation rules.

Manual entry: Registered users and administrators can create new well, fluid, rock, gas, or scale records using the built-in data entry window. Mandatory fields are marked in red.

During data entry, the system automatically validates units, formats, and mandatory fields to prevent inconsistencies or structural errors.

7.4 DATA EXPORT

Selected data can be exported in XLSX format for external use or further analysis. Users may export single wells or multiple selected wells (together with their associated datasets). All exported tables include essential metadata, ensuring full traceability and compliance with FAIR data principles.

8 MAINTENANCE, SUSTAINABILITY AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas is designed to remain operational and accessible beyond the lifetime of the CRM-geothermal project. Its long-term maintenance and hosting are ensured by the University of Miskolc, Institute of Information Technology (IIT), which provides a secure and stable infrastructure for both the database and the web application.

The system runs on dedicated servers at the University of Miskolc, under the supervision of the

technical staff of the Institute of Information Technology, who oversee performance, security, and data integrity. Regular backups are performed to prevent data loss, and version control ensures that all updates to the database and the web interface remain traceable. Communication between the client and the server is secured through HTTPS encryption, and user authentication is managed by a token-based system, preventing unauthorised access.

Routine maintenance tasks, such as correcting minor errors, updating software dependencies, or validating data consistency, are carried out by the IIT administrators. The University of Miskolc has committed to keeping the Fluid Atlas available after the project’s completion as part of its data infrastructure, thereby ensuring continued access for the research community. *Table 3* summarises the key roles involved in the administration, quality assurance, and governance of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas. It highlights the division of responsibilities among partners to ensure continuous system reliability, data quality, and long-term sustainability.

The modular design of the system allows for future expansion of the database content and gradual interface improvements without structural changes. New datasets from upcoming geothermal or CRM-related research projects can be integrated directly into the existing database, benefiting from the harmonised metadata framework established in CRM-geothermal. The direct data upload by registered users ensures that, after initial registration, the involvement of project administrators or IIT staff is not required for routine database updates. This approach enables a dynamically expanding database with built-in quality control mechanisms. Administrators periodically review the system to verify data integrity and harmonisation across all records.

This ensures that the Fluid Atlas remains a living, sustainable research infrastructure, supporting ongoing scientific collaboration, innovation, and data reuse in the field of geothermal energy and critical raw materials.

Table 3: Overview of administrative roles and responsibilities

Role / Function	Responsible Partner(s)	Main Responsibilities	Frequency / Timing
System Administrator	University of Miskolc IIT	Server management, security updates, HTTPS configuration, regular backups, uptime monitoring	Continuous; weekly system checks
Database Administrator	University of Miskolc MFK/GFZ	Supervise database; check metadata completeness	Continuous; monthly optimisation
Registered users	professionals in CRM or geothermal fields	Validate and enter/import new datasets	For each dataset at the publication
User Support Contact, administrator	University of Miskolc MFK/GFZ	Handle user queries; provide guidance on data access, citation, export formats; manage user registration and access rights	As required (≤ 5 working days response)
Governance Committee	CRM-geothermal Consortium	Strategic oversight; decide on future developments, data policy, and integration with EU infrastructures	Annual review

9 IMPACT

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas is not only a technical outcome but also a strategic tool supporting scientific progress, industrial innovation, and education in the field of geothermal energy and critical raw materials. By transforming harmonised geochemical and geological datasets into an open and interactive spatial resource, it enhances Europe’s capacity to manage subsurface resources in line with the green and digital transitions.

From a scientific perspective, the Atlas provides a FAIR-compliant platform that enables cross-regional comparison of geothermal systems and CRM occurrences in Europe and Eastern Africa. Researchers can identify patterns between fluids, rocks, and CRM concentrations, perform comparative geochemical analyses, and access validated, traceable datasets that support reproducibility and collaboration.

For industry and policy, the Atlas functions as a transparent knowledge base for assessing the CRM potential of geothermal resources and planning sustainable utilisation strategies. Its accessibility and harmonisation strengthen evidence-based decision-making and innovation across the geothermal value chain.

The platform also offers educational benefits, serving as a training and demonstration tool for students and professionals in geoscience and data management. By uniting legacy and newly obtained datasets under open-science principles, the Fluid Atlas provides a lasting foundation for future research, capacity building, and informed resource governance (*Table 4*).

Table 4: Overview of the impact of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas in different domains

Impact Area	Description	Main Users / Beneficiaries	Key Benefits
Scientific	Provides a FAIR, harmonised platform for geothermal and CRM data across Europe and Eastern Africa.	Researchers, universities, geological surveys	Enables cross-regional comparison; supports reproducibility and data sharing; interoperable with European platforms.
Industrial	Serves as a decision-support tool for assessing geothermal CRM potential.	Geothermal operators, mining companies, consultants	Identifies co-production opportunities; supports sustainable resource planning; promotes innovation.
Educational	Offers an interactive environment for teaching and training in geoscience and data management.	Universities, students, training centres	Enhances digital and geoscientific skills; supports teaching on geothermal and CRM systems.
Policy / Societal	Improves transparency and access to geothermal and CRM information for decision-makers and the public.	Policymakers, authorities, general public	Informs sustainable energy and raw materials policies; raises public awareness; supports EU Green Deal goals.

10 CONCLUSIONS

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas represents one of the key outcomes of the Horizon Europe project CRM-geothermal: Raw materials from geothermal fluids: occurrence, enrichment, extraction. It provides an open, harmonised, and spatially referenced database environment that brings together geothermal and critical raw material related data from across Europe and East Africa.

By integrating legacy datasets with newly obtained field and laboratory data, the Atlas delivers a

coherent framework for exploring the occurrence and enrichment of CRMs in geothermal systems. Its harmonised metadata structure, built in validation rules, and role based access model ensure both scientific reliability and long-term data integrity. Through the use of FAIR and open-science principles, all data are traceable, accessible, and reusable for future studies.

The modular architecture of the system, based on a MySQL database, Node.js backend, and Angular/Leaflet web interface, allows for continuous growth as new datasets are added by registered users. Hosting at the University of Miskolc guarantees long-term sustainability and secure maintenance of the infrastructure.

The Fluid Atlas thus provides a lasting, expandable platform that supports research, innovation, and policy development in the fields of geothermal energy and critical raw materials, ensuring that the knowledge generated within CRM-geothermal remains available for future scientific and industrial applications.

11 REFERENCES

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ANNEX 1 – USER GUIDE WITH SCREENSHOTS

Overview

The CRM-Geothermal Fluid Atlas and Database tool was developed within the framework of the Horizon Europe project “CRM-Geothermal – Raw materials from geothermal fluids: occurrence, enrichment, extraction.” The system was designed and implemented by the University of Miskolc, with contributions from project partners across Europe. It provides access to a comprehensive database of geothermal fluid, rock, well, and gas sample data. The tool allows users to search, visualize, and export datasets supporting research on critical raw materials in geothermal environments.

Getting started

The CRM-Geothermal web application can be accessed at <https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu>. The system has three access levels: User, Registered User, and Administrator. To ensure database security and maintain data quality, automatic registration is disabled. If you wish to become a registered user to contribute to the database, please contact Katrin Kieling (Project Coordinator, katrin.kieling@gfz.de) or Anna Seres (Leader of WP1, anna.seres@uni-miskolc.hu). The following sections describe the tools available to each access level, but in general Users can view, search, and export data, Registered Users can additionally upload and edit data, but may edit only their own uploads, and Administrators have full privileges on all data and can approve or remove user registrations. Tools only available for only registered users or admins are described in italics.

Detailed Features

The following pages present the main functions of the CRM-Geothermal web application through numbered screenshots and brief explanations. The tool consists of two primary views: the Database view (Figure A1.) and the Map view (Figure A7.). In the following guide, these are displayed in the two main images, where the numbered labels indicate the layout and functionality of each component. Additional smaller images illustrate what appears when specific functions are selected, helping you understand how to navigate, search, upload, edit, and export data in the system. To display the Map view properly, please enable location access in your browser and ensure that location services are turned on in your computer’s system settings.

Support

If you encounter any issues while using the CRM-Geothermal web application, or you have questions related to access rights, data upload, or system functionality, please contact Katrin Kieling (katrin.kieling@gfz.de) or Anna Seres (anna.seres@uni-miskolc.hu). Feedback and suggestions for improving the tool are also welcome.

Version Information

This document reflects the current functionality of the tool as of March, 2026 and will be updated as new features are introduced. Please refer to the project website or contact the project coordinators for the latest version.

15 Advanced search

1 Database 2 Map 3 User Management 4 5

22 20 Appendix

Choose file to import Export

Well Data Fluid Sample Data Rock Sample Data Gas Sample Data Scale Sample Data

Search 19 +

ID	Country	Local ID	Well Type	Name Of The Facility	Power thermal	Latitude	Longitude	Date Of Well Completion	Well Head Elevation	Surface Elevation	True Vertical Well Depth	Mea
W_AT_001	Austria	Blumau 2	Production well			47.12	16.04					
W_AT_002	Austria	Blumau 3				47.12	16.04					
W_AT_003	Austria	Blumau 1a	Injektion well			47.12	16.04					
W_AT_004		Georgsquelle				47.02	14.41					
W_AT_005		Mariaheilquelle				47.02	14.41					
W_AT_006		Ignazheilquelle				47.02	14.41					
W_AT_007	Austria	Michaelshelquelle				47.02	14.41					
W_AT_008	Austria	Hallenbadquelle				47.02	14.41					
W_AT_009	Austria	Tiefbohrung Wels				48.17	14.04					
		W_AT_009_FS_001			W_AT_009_RS_001							
W_AT_010	Austria	Ötbohrung Meggenhofen				48.18	13.8					
W_AT_011	Austria	Paracelsus-Quelle Bad Hall				48.04	14.21					
W_AT_012	Austria	Eiselbergs-Quelle Bad Hall				48.04	14.21					
W_AT_013	Austria	Feyreggerbach 1 Bad Hall				48.04	14.21					
W_AT_014	Austria	Feyreggerbach 2 Bad Hall				48.04	14.21					
W_AT_015	Austria	Furtmühle-Quelle Bad Hall				48.04	14.21					
W_AT_016	Austria	Gunterhöhen-Quelle Bad Hall				48.04	14.21					
W_AT_017	Austria	...				48.04	14.21					
W_AT_018	Austria	Sulzbach 2 Bad Hall				48.04	14.21					

17 Select none 18 Delete selected

Items per page: 20 1 - 20 of 3870

Figure A1: Database view of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and Database tool

DATABASE VIEW

Top navigation bar

1. Database: switch to the Database view here
2. Map: switch to the Map view here
3. *User management: adding or deleting users or changing their role is possible here. Accessible only to administrators.*
4. *User profile: checking and modifying username, name, institution and email address. Available to registered users and admins.*
5. Login/logout: login is only possible after registration from one of the administrators with the e-mails indicated above.

General structure, layout

6. Well, fluid, rock, gas and scale data on different sheets
7. Attributes of the data
8. List of wells, fluids, etc
9. ID of fluid, rock, gas or scale, belonging the given well. Clicking on it takes you to the chosen fluid, rock, etc data.
10. Number of wells, fluids, etc by page

Data management

11. *View data: Data of the selected well, fluid, gas, rock or scale in a view window. The small globe icon shows the location of the selected well. Figure A2., A3.*
12. *Edit data: Data of the selected well, fluid, gas, rock or scale in an edit window. Here you can modify any data, but only in case it is data you uploaded yourself. Administrators can modify any data. The small globe icon shows the location of the selected well to help ensure the coordinates are correct. Available to registered users and admins. Figure A4.*
13. *Delete data: Deletes the selected data. Registered users can only delete (or edit) the data uploaded by themselves. Admins can delete any data. Deleting a well deletes all the corresponding fluids, rocks, gases and scales.*

Well Data
✕

Basic Info ^

Well ID:	W_AT_001
Local ID:	Blumau 2
Country:	Austria
Facility Name:	
Well Type:	Production well
Latitude:	47.12°
Longitude:	16.04°
Date Of Well Completion:	
Power Thermal:	-

Depth & Elevation ^

Well Head Elevation:	-
Surface Elevation:	-
True Vertical Well Depth:	-
Measured Well Depth:	2843 m

Figure A2. Data view window for wells

Country: Austria
 Country code: AT
 Latitude: 48.17
 Longitude: 14.04

OK

Figure A3. Location check with the globe icon

Figure A4. Data editor window for wells

Search options, selections

14. General search: free-text search. It searches for the typed characters in the whole dataset of the active sheet. E.g. if the Well sheet is active, the search will be conducted in the whole well sheet, it does not have to be related to any attribute, but the search will not run for the other sheets

15. Advanced search: searches for the values of each attribute. More than one search criteria can be added from different sheets. In this latter case there is “AND” relation between the different criteria. Figure A5.

16. Checkmark for selecting data in case more wells, fluids, rocks, gases or scales need to be deleted or exported at once

17. Select all/Select none: Select all: Selects all items on the active sheet. If no search was made, this means all wells, fluids, etc. If a search was conducted previously, select all selects the result of the search. Select none: clears selection. You can remove all checkmarks from the active sheet (well, fluid, rock, etc)

18. Delete selected: deletes the selected rows (marked with a checkmark). In case a well is deleted, the corresponding fluids, rocks, gases and scales are also deleted.

Sample	Attribute	Operator	Value	Value
Well	Outflow Temperature	greater than	70	
Well	Well Yield	greater than	100	
Fluid	Li	greater than	50	
		equals		

Figure A5. Advanced search of CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and Database tool

Data import/export

19. Add new well/fluid/rock/gas/scale sample: A new item can be added and the data typed in through the data edit window. Fields marked with red are mandatory. Available to registered users and admins. Figure A6.

20. Choose file to import: Adding new data is possible in two ways. One is typing the data directly into the tool through the tool's data edit interface, see in previous point. The other option is importing it from an excel file with this button. In order to successfully upload the data, it has to be in the official CRM-geothermal excel template, available for download from <https://crm-geothermal.eu/>.

21. Export: You can export selected data into xlsx format.

22. Appendix: You can download the files:

- CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas User Guide
- Guidelines for Data Collection
- CRM-geothermal data Collection Template

Well Data

Well ID * format: W_HU_002	Name of the facility	Country*
Local ID for well*	Date of well completion year	Latitude*
Well type	Power MWth	Longitude*

Wellhead elevation amsl	True vertical well depth m	Top of screened interval m	Top of screened interval m
Surface elevation amsl	Measured well depth m	Bottom of screened interval m	Bottom of screened interval m
Hydraulic head amsl	PZ data MPa/	PZ data depth m	

Bottomhole temperature °C	Outflow temperature °C	Well yield m³/	Scaling exists ▼
Depth of measured bottomhole temp m	Year of outflow temp. measurement year	Year of well yield measurement year	Inhibitor added ▼
References for the data		Remarks on well yield measurement	Geothermal gradient in °C/100m

Save data Cancel

Figure A6. Add new data window for wells. Fields marked with red are mandatory

Figure A7. Map view of CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and Database tool.

MAP VIEW

General structure, layout

23. List of wells: The left side of the view shows the list of the wells, while the right side shows their location on the map.
- 24, 25. Corresponding fluid, rock, gas and scale ID: If the well has fluid, rock, gas or scale data, the ID of these can be seen by clicking the well. Clicking on these ID shows the fluid, rock etc. data in the data view window.

Data Management

26. View data: data of the given well can be seen in the data view window.
27. Location pin: The map zooms in to the selected well, when clicked on it.

Search options, selections

28. General search: free-text search. It searches for the typed characters in the whole dataset of the sheet selected beside the search box (W-well, F-fluid, R-rock, G-gas, S-scale). E.g. if the W is selected, the search will be conducted in the whole well sheet, it does not have to be related to any attribute, but the search will not run for the other sheets
29. Advanced search: searches for the values of each attribute. More than one search criteria can be added from different sheets. In this latter case there is “AND” relation between the different criteria. Figure A5.
30. Select all/select none: Select all: Selects all wells. If no search was made, this means all wells of the database. If a search was conducted previously, select all selects the result of the search. Select none: clears selection. All checkmarks are removed.
31. Circle on the map: clicking on any circle on the map selects the corresponding well, which appears in the left pane.

Graduated colour view

32. Selection box for graduated colour view: Any numerical variables can be represented on the map by graduated colours. Select datasheet first (W-well, F-fluid, R-rock, G-gas, S-scale), then from the drop down menu, select the desired numerical element, property, etc..
33. Minimum and maximum value of the selected numerical variable in the database.
34. Minimum value of the selected variable in the current map extent
35. Maximum value of the selected variable in the current map extent
36. Map navigation and box selection: pins/wells can be selected by drawing a rectangle on the map by holding the right mouse button.
37. Coordinate and country of the selected well.

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